

Bioefficacy of Acetone Leaf Extract of *Azadiracta indica* A. Juss on Growth of *Macrophomina phaseolina* Causing Root Rot Disease of Sarpagandha (*Rauwolfia serpentina*) by using different Concentrations

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ABSTRACT

Macrophomina phaseolina (Tassi) Goid is a soil borne fungus causes root rot diseases to Sarpagandha (*Rauwolfia serpentina*). The fungus infects the root and lower stem of over 500 plant species and is widely distributed in the United States (Wyllie, 1988). The bioefficacy of *Azadiracta indica* A. Juss Acetone leaf extract against growth of *Macrophomina phaseolina* was studied by using Acetone as a solvent at different concentrations i.e., 1.00, 2.00, 3.00, 4.00, 5.00, 6.00, 7.00, 8.00, 9.00 and 10.00 % for their antifungal efficacy.

Keywords: *Macrophomina phaseolina*, Sarpagandha, *Azadiracta indica*, Acetone

INTRODUCTION

Macrophomina phaseolina (Tassi) Goid is a soil borne fungus causes root rot diseases to Sarpagandha (*Rauwolfia serpentina*). The fungus infects the root and lower stem of several plant species and is widely distributed in the United States (Wyllie, 1988).

The fungal pathogen *Macrophomina phaseolina* (Tassi) Goid was isolated from the *Rauwolfia serpentina* roots collected from medicinal plant garden, V. N. M. A. University, Parbhani and Medicinal plant garden, M. P. K. V., Rahuri showing typical root rot symptoms i.e. black conductive tissue. The infected roots were sterilized with 0.5% sodium hypochlorite solution. The sterilized root were used for isolation of fungal pathogen i.e. *Macrophomina phaseolina*. The Locally available *Azadiracta indica* (Neem) plant leaves were used for preparation of Acetone leaf extract. The Methanolic leaf extract was used to study their efficacy against *Macrophomina phaseolina* by poisoned food technique in vitro as used by Shiva et.al, (2008) and Francis Borgio, et.al, (2008) to know their inhibitory effect on the growth of *Macrophomina phaseolina*.

The different concentrations used were as 1.00, 2.00, 3.00, 4.00, 5.00, 6.00, 7.00, 8.00, 9.00 and 10.00 percent. The acetone extract was tested against growth of *Macrophomina phaseolina* for 7 days incubation at room temperature and results are expressed as percent inhibition.

Preparation of Acetone plant part extracts:

Healthy fresh leaves of *Azadiracta indica* (Neem) plant was taken and washed thoroughly with fresh water and finally rinsed with sterile distilled water and dried.

Fifty gram of dried leaves, rhizomes and bulbs of different plants were cut into small pieces and grinded in a grinder to make fine powder and then extracted in 50 ml Acetone. Extracts thus, obtained were filtered through double layered muslin cloth in 150 ml flasks and plugged. The extracts then autoclaved at pressure 15 lbs for 20 minutes. Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) medium was prepared and sterilized at 15 lbs pressure for 20 minutes. The sterilized extracts were considered as standard plant extracts and used for the testing of antifungal activity. The different concentrations were prepared i.e., 1.00, 2.00, 3.00, 4.00, 5.00, 6.00, 7.00, 8.00, 9.00 and 10.00 percent. The 1 ml extracts of different concentrations were individually added in 15 ml melted, cooled and sterilized PDA at the time of pouring in the petriplates and incubated at room temperature. After solidification a 5 mm disc of actively growing 7 days old pure culture of *Macrophomina phaseolina* was incubated aseptically in the centre of plate. Three repetitions were made for each treatment. Medium without phytoextracts served as control. The

observations of fungal growth in diameter were observed and recorded and percent growth inhibition was also worked out. Khajista, et.al. (2013).

The sclerotial formation was determined by observing number of sclerotia per microscopic field

Experimental results:

Table 1 and Fig 1 shows the efficacy of *Azadiracta indica* A. Juss against *Macrophomina phaseolina* was studied by using acetone as solvent at different concentrations i.e., 1.00, 2.00, 3.00, 4.00 5.00 ,6.00, 7.00, 8.00, 9.00 and 10.00 % for their antifungal property with the help of standard poisoned food technique.

Azadiracta indica efficacy at 1 % concentration shows 14.25 to 55.88 %, at 2% concentration gives 15.28 to 58.00 %, at 3 % concentration shows 16.90 to 61.90 %, at 4 % concentration gives 17.97 to 64.00% , at 5 % concentration gives 18.68 to 67.27 %, at 6% concentration shows 19.75 to 70.10, at 7% concentration gives 22.00 to 76.90, at 8 % concentration gives 25.30 to 84.22, at 9% concentration shows 27.35 to 88.74 and at 10 % concentration gives 29.53 to 90.19 inhibition of the growth of the pathogen with acetone solvent viz. recorded at 1 to 7 days of incubation period.

Table -1: Effect of acetone leaves extract of *Azadiracta indica* A. Juss on growth of *Macrophomina phaseolina*.

Incubation Period (Days)	Control (Acetone)	Percent inhibition									
		Concentration (%)									
		1.00	2.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	6.00	7.00	8.00	9.00	10.00
1	8.15 (5.22)	14.25 (18.19)	15.28 (8.78)	16.90 (9.72)	17.97 (10.35)	18.68 (10.76)	19.75 (11.39)	22.00 (12.70)	25.30 (14.65)	27.35 (15.87)	29.53 (17.17)
2	10.24 (5.87)	24.22 (14.01)	27.30 (15.84)	29.89 (17.39)	31.56 (18.39)	33.78 (19.74)	35.00 (20.48)	37.80 (22.20)	39.35 (23.17)	42.35 (25.05)	45.98 (27.37)
3	11.55 (6.63)	30.35 (17.66)	32.00 (18.66)	34.90 (20.42)	36.45 (21.37)	38.23 (22.7)	40.45 (23.85)	42.36 (25.06)	46.45 (27.67)	53.50 (32.34)	56.48 (34.38)
4	13.00 (7.46)	36.44 (21.36)	38.00 (22.33)	40.34 (23.78)	42.45 (25.11)	44.00 (26.10)	46.78 (27.88)	49.00 (29.33)	52.00 (31.33)	60.00 (36.86)	63.17 (39.17)
5	16.44 (9.46)	42.00 (24.83)	45.25 (26.90)	48.54 (29.03)	51.90 (31.26)	53.78 (32.53)	56.00 (34.05)	58.79 (36.00)	62.54 (38.70)	68.14 (42.95)	72.53 (47.00)
6	18.35 (10.57)	49.85 (30.03)	53.58 (32.54)	56.89 (34.89)	59.80 (36.96)	61.34 (38.10)	64.90 (40.77)	68.17 (43.36)	74.95 (49.10)	75.15 (49.33)	83.38 (57.64)
7	22.10 (12.76)	55.88 (34.18)	58.00 (35.67)	61.90 (38.44)	64.00 (40.10)	67.27 (42.53)	70.10 (44.94)	76.90 (50.77)	84.22 (58.81)	88.74 (64.49)	90.19 (64.42)
S.E ±	0.42	2.27	2.30	2.30	2.38	2.42	2.55	2.52	3.34	3.41	3.16
C.D at 5%	1.30	7.00	7.10	7.08	7.33	7.45	7.86	7.78	10.30	10.51	9.73

Fig.-1: Bioefficacy of acetone leaves extract of *Azadiracta indica* A. Juss on of *Macrophomina phaseolina*.

DISCUSSION

The efficacy of acetone leaf extract of *Azadiracta indica*, at 1 % concentration gives 14.25 percent as minimum inhibition of growth of the *Macrophomina phaseolina* pathogen with first day incubation period and at 1 % concentration gives 55.88 percent as maximum inhibition of growth of the *Macrophomina phaseolina* pathogen with seven day incubation period. The efficacy of acetone leaf extract of *Azadiracta indica*, at 10 % concentration gives 29.53 percent as minimum inhibition of growth of the *Macrophomina phaseolina* pathogen with first day incubation period and at 10 % concentration gives 90.19 percent as maximum inhibition of growth of the *Macrophomina phaseolina* pathogen with seven day incubation period.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

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REFERENCES

- Cloud GL, Rupe JC (1991) Comparison of three media for enumeration of sclerotia of *Macrophomina phaseolina*. Plant Disease 75:771-772.
- Dhavle SD, Kareppa BM, Maske VS, Rathod LR (2008) Utilization of *Allium cepa* leaf extracts on linear growth of *Colletotrichum capsici*. Bionano Frontier 2(1).
- Dhavle SD, Aglave HR, Kareppa BM (2012) Utilization of leaf extract of *Withania somnifera* L. Dual on linear growth of *Colletotrichum capsici*. Thematics Journal of Botany 1(4):37-38.
- Francis Borgio J, Jesvin Bency B, Neha Sharma (2008) Compatibility of *Metarhizium anisopliae* (Metsch) Sorok with *Ocimum sanctum* L. (Tulsi) extracts. Journal of Ethnobotanical Leaflets 12:698-704.
- Khajista Jabeen, Nidra Waheed, Sumera Iqbal (2013) Antifungal potential of *Calotropis procera* against *Macrophomina phaseolina*. Life Science Journal 10(12s).
- Shiva N, Ganesan S, Banumathy N, Muthuchelian (2008) Antifungal effect of leaf extract of some medicinal plant against *Fusarium oxysporum* causing wilt disease of *Solanum melongena* L. Ethnobotanical Leaflets 12:156-163.
- Wyllie TD (1988) Charcoal rot of soybean-current status. In: Wyllie TD, Scott DH (eds) Soybean diseases of the north central region. APS Press, St. Paul, MN.

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